

DESIGN OF CONSUMER THERMAL SUBSTATIONS FOR THE INTEGRATION OF DISTRIBUTED SOLAR TECHNOLOGIES IN DISTRICT HEATING SYSTEMS

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Solar thermal systems

- Increasing levels of incorporation of solar thermal (ST) systems in buildings.
 - (most) ST systems sized to meet a fraction of the heat load of buildings
- Large ST plants and Thermal Storage in DH networks is possible.
 - Limited by geographical constraints and scarcity of land in larger cities.
- NZEB+ST will result in excess production during large parts of the year.
- Steady reductions in DH temperatures facilitate the connection of ST and DH.

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Connection schemes at building level

Various approaches:

- Isolated ST system
- DH as back-up heat source
- DH as back-up heat source, delivery of ST excess heat to DH
- Full interconnection of ST, DH and building in central manifolds/substation.

Fully integrated systems are estimated to produce a 50% surplus energy than other connections.

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Basic Design of Substations

Heat delivery modes

- DH to load (space heating & DHW)
- Solar to load (space heating & DHW)
- Solar to DH

Specificities

- Bidirectional/net heat meters
- Local pump for reverse pumping from return to service pipes

RELaTED, A FLEXIBLE APPROACH TO THE DEPLOYMENT AND CONVERSION OF DH NETWORKS TO LOW TEMPERATURE, WITH INCREASED USE OF LOCAL SOLAR SYSTEMS

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Expected development

RELaTED will be demonstrated in 4 selected locations:

- Green field development in VINGE, DK
- DH network with large share of biomass in TARTU, EE
- Large DH network with incorporation of large RES resources in BELGRADE, SR
- Corporate DH network in IURRETA, ES

Project partners: TECNALIA, Danish Technical Institute, Fortum Tartu, Beogradske Elektrane, Basque Government, Metro Therm, Nibe, Aventa, Industrias IMAR, Basque Energy Agency, Mazovia Energy Agency, Institute of Baltic Studies, FEDARENE, El Taller De Comunicación y CIA.

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